

The Choice Modeling Approach To Analyzed Hospital Quality Parameters In Indonesia

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Abstract

This paper investigates how the choice modeling approach is used to assess the effect of dominant factors on patient preferences in Indonesia over two years. The dominant factors include distance, cost of health expenditure, and quality outcome. We focus on B-Class hospitals operated either by the state or through private or military institutions. These results indicate that patient's health access (distance) and delivering health quality providers (mortality rate, income group, and severity level significantly affect patient preference. The UHC is still a challenge for a large country like Indonesia. The UHC must increase access capacity and health service quality in order to achieve success in Indonesia.

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Introduction

At this moment, there is an urgent need for government to get information, how to improve the public and patient preference of clinical/policy decision making in clinical/public health programs. Predicting information on expected demand for a public health program is crucial. The revealed preferences method inform the public policy market on how (1) public or private insurance consumers face market prices; (2) how health policy that connects between patient and health service provider observed consumption that solely based on patient preferences; (3) the proper intervention of government in a particular market to maximize public goods (Lancsar & Louviere, 2008). In the past two decades, discrete choice experiment (DCE) is a powerful approach to analyzing this issue (Broek-Altenburg & Atherly, 2020). The DCE can mimic elicit preferences and value for goods/services in the service market. The approach can measure patient preferences with the joint decision between patient and health service providers accordingly. In several studies, such as Grépin et al. (2018); Gutacker et al. (2015) reported that DCE is an adequate method to guide decisions about allocating external financing for health with stakeholders mapping. We can state that the DCE could bring out health care outcomes, especially inpatient preferences.

As we noted earlier that, the DCE could reveal the elicit preferences. The data is typically obtained from the existing claims patient's data and electronic health records (Broek-Altenburg & Atherly, 2020). The data include patient records and health service providers that connect how health service providers are assessed from a consumer perspective. The DCE may be helpful to construct consumer choice analysis. This method can assist policymakers in analyzing individuals' decision-making process on how choosing between treatment options is usually hard to measure the choice in between. We can evaluate the quality of health care service delivery of hospital options such as hospitals operated by states or private by decomposing the preference analysis into aggregated patient evaluation for each health service provider. Gaynor et al. (2016a) reported that The DCE could assist policymakers in investigating how health insurance reform affects patients' decision to get better medication in the UK. How do quality factors such as mortality rate, distance, income group, and health report status affect a patient visit? Furthermore, Gutacker et al. (2015) highlighted that improving quality service, such as decreasing mortality rate, reducing the distance for health access, reducing waiting time, and proper medication for comorbidity in health service providers, improves patient visits. Nevertheless, choice modeling is a powerful tool for assessing quality from consumer choice perspectives.

According to our best knowledge, the paper that conducts The DCE approach for evaluating health service insurance, especially for the UHC, is rare, especially for emerging economies like Indonesia. Nowadays, the UHC is a crucial issue to every country to fulfill SDGs goals; as noted by United Nations (2019) that every country has to compromise with the initiative and declared that UHC is imperative for all people. There is an urgent requirement for both policymakers and academicians to explore and need more examples for other countries how the UHC is implemented. What is a driven factor for removing the UHC's obstacles and promoted them across the globe? A case study of Indonesia's UHC as emerging economies can contribute to the global evidence for understanding UHC that requires equity in access, quality of health services, and financial protection as essential relative objectives. This study will be imperative for contributing to the importance of UHC policy.

This is the first study that assesses the effect of consumer choice with the largest sample of The UHC's study in Indonesia. The study will assist other economies in improving UHC health policy across the world. Indonesia is a middle-income country with 262 million inhabitants. The area spans from Aceh to Papua and consists of 17,744 islands that equal London to Tehran. This unique geographic characteristic has put Indonesia in a challenging situation with high mortality from infectious disease and poverty, as well as the chronic problem of non-communicable diseases (Naghavi et al., 2015). Although standard health care has been introduced, the outcomes vary by state and between private providers (Mboi, 2015). In 2004, Indonesia enacted law no. 40/2004, regarding the National Social Security System, and henceforth has been a country with Universal Health Coverage (UHC). To run UHC, Indonesia created the Social Security Administrative Body (BPJS) in 2014 as an independent government body to address this policy. The UHC (also known as the JKN, *Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional - National Health Insurance*) was established to create a well-integrated, sustainable, accessible, and equitable health system that provides primary and advanced care service with high-quality service for all Indonesians (Mboi, 2015). The World Bank (2017) reported that Indonesia has struggled to manage the health financing transition and build a sustainable UHC, despite solid growth in total health expenditure. Although the overall service has improved, the demand still does not fully meet the requirements. We argue that the quality of health care is a major issue to resolve the problem.

In order to investigate this issue, we propose that The DCE method can be applied to investigate the quality factors on UHC implementation in Indonesia. We investigate how hospital quality is assessed through patient preferences about a hospital's health care delivery quality. It is similar to the study by Panpiemras et al. (2011) that investigated UHC implementation in Thailand without the DCE; however, this research is conducted in Indonesia, with the DCT method. We predict consumer choice based upon choice modeling that represents the accurate behavior of UHC's consumer preferences due to its huge dataset (more than 300.000 samples.). We focus on advanced health care service due to hospital health care service merely in this stage. The Ministry of Health has introduced Ministry Regulation No. 56/2014 for hospital classification and permits: this regulation classifies hospitals into A-Class, B-Class, C-Class, and D-Class. A-class, the highest classification level, denotes hospitals as the best and most sophisticated healthcare service providers in terms of human resources, such as qualified physicians, nurses, and other health care professionals. In addition, Taher (2014) stated that B-class hospitals should be more widely available across the region. The B-Class hospital is less expensive than A-Class hospitals. It provides more excellent quality in terms of human resources and health infrastructure than C-Class or D-Class hospitals. Along with the UHC system, the government has made a significant effort to improve the quality of health service in Indonesia.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis

2.1. Literature Review

The basic theory of this research-based is to enhance consumer choice for public service (Besley & Ghatak, 2003) how government can produce public health service that fits for all (Cotlear et al., 2015). According to Donabedian model, health service quality consists of patient satisfaction, health status, recovery, improvement, nosocomial infection, iatrogenic illnesses, rehospitalization, mortality, incidence, and prevalence of diseases (Shi & Singh, 2019). Docteur et al. (1996) stated that the outcome of healthcare access of medicine produces mortality as the paramount status of equity of healthcare services besides morbidity, well-being, and functioning. The policymakers can assess clinical and policy outcomes, which inform us whether these factors affect consumer preferences or not. According to previous research, such as Gutacker et al. (2016), Gaynor et al. (2016), Beckert et al. (2012), Moscone et al. (2012) Geweke et al., (2003), the mortality rate is simple and powerful parameters that indicate how healthcare service delivery can improve demand. When the mortality rate is higher, it is strongly related to the clinical quality of the hospital. The clinical aspects of mortality rate include health care service facilities, the qualifications and skills of caregivers, the cost-efficiency of care, and the

results of patient's health (Shi & Singh, 2019). The higher mortality rate reduces consumer preferences and demand of the hospital.

Public health service reduces inequality in that every level of citizen receives basic standard of health care delivery such as cost, access, and quality (Shi & Singh, 2019). These premises have been challenged by uneven progress due to lack of specific action (Friedman et al., 2019), financial difficulties, deteriorating quality, a barrier of access (Panpiemras et al., 2011; Gutacker et al., 2016). Especially in developing countries, there is no clear cut on how the utilization of health care finance by Universal Health Coverage (UHC) leads to change in patient behaviour (Bernales-Baksai, 2020).

2.2. Hypothesis

We hypothesize that the provision of health care will remain unchanged in the short term, and patient preferences drive the health care service. We assume the fixed effect in the model-based upon administrative boundaries that indicated the increase of health service providers is time-variant, during the administrative boundaries in the time-invariant. The UHC attracts the supply without explicit investment but increasing participation within administrative boundaries. The rigidity in supply is determined by two significant factors: healthcare service providers and the cost of healthcare expenditure. When the supply of health care providers is unchanged over a short period, the demand will be less responsive due to limited access. The patients are restricted in their access to quality health care providers (Gaynor et al., 2016). The demand for UHC is, ideally, equal to the growth of participating UHC service providers.

The supply of health care providers is defined by the distance between hospitals and patients. When the distance between patient and hospital is getting shorter, it stimulates transport cost efficiency such as travel time and waiting time for health care (Moscelli et al., 2016). The patients prefer to travel the shortest distance to a healthcare provider. It indicates that the slope between distance and patient choice of a particular hospital will be negative and steeper, as the patients are in closest proximity of health care.

Another supply parameter is the cost of health expenditure. When cost capitation is adequate for health care service in the UHC, it will improve consumer preferences through better health care services by health care service providers. A recent report in the US shows that the underfunding of public health increases the risk to the public health system (McKillop & Ilakkuvan, 2019). We argue that cost has a negative relationship rather than a positive relationship due to the insufficient capitation system in Indonesia, as Satibi et al. (2019) and Shreeshant et al. (2019) noted.

Furthermore, from the demand side, that linked into supply-side such as Mortality rate, Income Group, and Severity Level. We hypothesized that better management of health service providers reduces mortality rate and cost, quality, and access (Shi & Singh, 2019). The mortality rate will have a negative relationship with patient preferences: previous studies, such as Gutacker et al. (2016), McConnel et al. (2015), Beckert et al. (2012), Moscone et al. (2012), and Pope (2009) have stated that mortality rate is a measure of health service provider quality. We stated that the Mortality rate has a positive effect on consumer preferences. We argue that the increase of regulation portrayed in Mboi (2015) has an effect on decreasing of Mortality rate. As noted by Trisnantoro & Listyani (2018), the growth of hospitals in Indonesia will at least improve access and reduce the mortality rate across the island.

While the mortality rate connects to the level of income group, higher-income groups are positively correlated (Pampel et al., 2010) with better diet, a more active daily life, access to healthier food, less stress, and a lower mortality rate (Loef & Walach, 2012). Gaynor et al. (2016a) support that the healthy lifestyle of higher-income groups reduces the cost of health insurance claims in the UK. We argue that income group and mortality rate in Indonesia negatively affect consumer preferences when the mortality rate in this group decreases; hence, patients improve their preferences. The means that hospitals provide better health care delivery by reducing the health outcome in this income group. If the parameter is positive, the UHC will finance more risky members that will risk healthy financing in the future.

The second interaction is Mortality rate with a severity level of morbidity. This interaction is helpful to show how health service providers can improve health. Previous studies, such as Gaynor et al. (2016), show that higher mortality represents a lower quality of treatment. We argue that interaction between Mortality Rate and

Morbidity Rate has a negative effect on consumer preferences. The improving number of healthcare service providers such as hospitals reduces morbidity rates, as noted by Trisnantoro & Listyani (2018).

In the last hypothesis, we test whether the demand for the UHC is increasing due to the health access indicators, as noted by Friedman et al., (2019) and Bernales-Baksai (2020). We empirically estimate how distance affects consumer preferences between 2015-2016 according to Sivey (2012) approaches. These results test whether two parameters are changed due to increasing patient visits to utilize the UHC scheme. We argue that the UHC will improve a patient visits to utilize health service providers in 2016.

3. Research Methods and Materials

3.1. Data

Samples of UHC patients and health service providers were supplied by the INA-CBG BPJS online system from 2015 and 2016. The samples were taken about 202 (89.3%) of 226 B-Class hospitals. The INA-CBG system is based on the Ministry of Health Regulation No. 52/2016 on the Health Standard Service for Health Insurance Services (HIS). The data is connected through the UHC membership card system, with a dataset representing 111 variables: 15 for patient id and membership; 23 about the primary health service provider; 20 variables for non-capitation; and 53 for the advanced health service provider. This study focuses on the advanced health care providers because this data represents the hospital healthcare system. The total sample number for both years is 909,202: 395,016 from 2015 and 514,186 from 2016. We obtained sample data about 79.1% of the total hospital sample.

The total sample for B-class hospitals is 34.6% (314.547 samples) for both periods. For each period, the data was collected about 37.5% (148.236 samples) in 2015 and 32.3% (166.311 samples) in 2016. These datasets are the largest sample than other A-class hospitals that consist about 17.5%, and C-class hospitals about 29.3% for both periods.

3.2. Research Methods

Before we move to econometric estimation, the first step that we should build is theoretically underpinned how the research question can be answered. We embarked on the preference theory as noted by Carpenter & Nakamoto (1989). We illustrated, there is three choices for the UHC patient to get health care medication i.e. state, military, and private B-class hospital. In contrast, we assumed that the UHC is close to public goods. The patient will prefer to visit B-Class hospital that operated by states and military rather than private. These conditions can be depicted as follow,

Figure 1. Graph Illustration of Three Choices Problem of B-Class Hospital

Figure 1, portrayed how patients have three options to get health care services from the UHC. The patient has only two priority choices, whereas the private is the last choice to some extent. The first patient's choice that indicated in A's point represents how a patient has preferences for Military" rather than State'. Otherwise, the choice is a change to B's point that represents how the patient's preferences move its choice from A towards B due to state hospital improve its service of quality. It increases State' to State'' and reduces Military" to Military'. This Graph demonstrated how the health service quality affects hospital preferences due to improvement of quality parameters.

These three options for choice of patient – i in operated hospital $j, j \in \{\text{states, military, private}\}$ can derived into utility maximizing behaviour as follows (Train, 2009),

$$U_{ijt}^{ID} = \beta_{ijt}^{ID'} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^n X_{ijt}^{n,ID} + \epsilon_{ijt}^{ID} \quad (1)$$

Where U_{ijt}^{ID} is the utility of patient i in hospital j in period t in Indonesia; $\beta_{ijt}^{ID'}$ is vector parameter effect of $\sum_{n=1}^n X_{ijt}^{n,ID}$ as n^{th} exogenous factors (i.e. quality factors of $\sum_{n=1}^n X_{ijt}^{n,ID}$ such as $D = \text{distance}$, $C = \text{Capitation Expenditure}$, $M = \text{mortality rate}$, $M \times Y = \text{mortality rate in highest income group}$, $M \times SL = \text{mortality rate in highest severity level}$) or quality vector of a patient's i in hospital's j at period t that effect on patient preferences; ϵ_{ijt}^{ID} is random error. This equation informs us how the exogenous factor affect patient's preferences that shift from X's point into Y's point.

While the choice is a binary option of three options hence, the value for the density function of patient preference is basically from an ordinary logit model with three sets of options. Thereby, the probability of condition whether the patient chooses those options will be selected according to condition on $\beta_{ijt}^{ID'}$ factors; hence we have,

$$P_{ijt}^{ID} = \int L_{ijt}^{ID}(\beta_{ijt}^{ID'}) f(\beta_{ijt}^{ID'} | \theta) d\beta_{ijt}^{ID'} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Where } L_{ijt}^{ID}(\beta_{ijt}^{ID'}) = \frac{e^{\beta_{ijt}^{ID'} \sum_{n=1}^n X_{ijt}^{n,ID}}}{\sum_{i=1}^i e^{\beta_{ijt}^{ID'} \sum_{n=1}^n X_{ijt}^{n,ID}}}$$

Where L is a logit function for three options of an operated hospital, therefore the X's factor that shifted that change of probability of P_{ijt}^{ID} . As portrayed in Figure 1, the shifting from A's point to B's point can be translated

into equation (2) that the change of P_{ijt}^{ID} as the probability distribution of patient to select his/her hospital determined by hospital's quality factors. While we have three options, or called multinomial logit, we can estimate equation (2) into three steps of calculation. First, we estimate equation (2) by drawing value from $f(\beta_{ijt}^{ID} | \theta)$ as the first draw; Second, we calculate logit estimation of $L_{ijt}^{ID}(\beta_{ijt}^{ID})$ that produce revised parameter; (3) repeated these step (1) and (2) many times and average the results. This average of results called simulated probability,

$$\hat{P}_{ijt}^{ID} = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R L_{ijt}^{ID}(\beta_{ijt}^{ID}) \quad (3)$$

Where R is the number of draws, \hat{P}_{ijt}^{ID} is an unbiased estimator of P_{ijt}^{ID} as noted in equation (2). There is some trade-off using a simulated probability of equation (3), along with increasing the R, it increases the variance of estimation (3). Thereby, equation (3) solved through simulated log-likelihood,

$$SLL = \sum_{i=1}^i \sum_{j=1}^j d_{ij} \ln \hat{P}_{ijt}^{ID} \quad (4)$$

Where d_{ij} is dummy choice of patient- i to visit hospital j , and zero otherwise. How the estimation achieved robustness results? When simulated maximum likelihood estimator in equation (4) achieved maximizing value of θ .

Furthermore, we estimated utility function ($U_{i,t}^{ID}$) in equation (1). The states hospital was set as a baseline outcome because it has the largest sample size and provides a better variance estimate. Hence, we can estimate equation (1) as a consumer preferences equation based upon multinomial logit choice according to equation (4) that given by,

$$U_{i,t}^{ID} = \alpha_{i,t}^{ID} + \beta_t^{D,ID} \cdot D_{i,t}^{ID} + \beta_t^{C,ID} \cdot C_{i,t}^{ID} + \beta_{i,t}^{M,ID} \cdot M_{i,t}^{ID} + \beta_{i,t}^{MY,ID} \cdot (M_{i,t}^{ID} \times Y_{i,t}^{ID}) + \beta_{i,t}^{MSL,ID} \cdot (M_{i,t}^{ID} \times SL_{i,t}^{ID}) + v_{i,t}^{ID} \quad (5)$$

$U_{i,t}^{ID}$ is consumer preferences that indicates the decision of patient- i to go to health services providers that operated by j - hospital indicates in binary variable ($U_{i,t}^r = 1$ or $U_{i,t}^r = 0$). Equation (1) stated that decision of patient for choosing in existing selected preferences hospital determined by $\sum_{n=1}^n X_{ijt}^{n,ID}$ that consist of distance ($D_{i,t}^{ID}$), cost of health expenditure (capitation system) $C_{i,t}^{ID}$, mortality rate ($M_{i,t}^{ID}$), interaction variables of Mortality and Highest Income Group ($MY_{i,t}^{ID}$), and Mortality Rate and Severity Level ($MSL_{i,t}^{ID}$). The magnitude of $\beta_t^{D,ID}$ is the distance parameter that patient travels to visit the health service provider operated by j -hospital within a particular period within the fixed effect assumption. $\beta_t^{C,ID}$ is the amount of health expenditure for each disease at health service providers of j within a particular period of time, t , with a random coefficient assumption. The quality covariates consist of mortality rates ($\beta_{ijt}^{M,ID}$), and the interaction variables of Mortality Rate \times Income Group ($\beta_{ijt}^{MY,ID}$), and Mortality Rate \times Severity Level ($\beta_{ijt}^{MSL,ID}$) as a proxy for morbidity level of patient at health service provider i , in a particular period time, t . $v_{i,t}^{ID}$ is the error terms for unobserved hospital characteristics and random utility.

Distance ($D_{i,t}^{ID}$) is treated as a fixed coefficient to capture the observed variation in-hospital characteristics, within the health service provider coverage, over time (2015 – 2016). We assumed that fixed effect according to geographic boundaries in particular geographic areas could be fixed; otherwise, there is an increasing number of hospitals in a particular area affect consumer preferences. The data was produced by calculating the distance between the primary healthcare providers to the B-class hospital. The distance (in km) for each patient to the B-Class hospital was estimated by applying a Geographical Information System (GIS) analysis.

It is assumed that the capitation cost of the UHC ($C_{i,t}^{ID}$) will have a positive effect on patient preferences: when the capitation cost is adequate with health care expenditure, the patient will have better medication and a greater preference for the health service provider. Therefore, since the health service provider is under-financing, this will reduce health service delivery to patients in the UHC scheme. Data from the capitation payment (in Rp) that patients' claimed was obtained from the INA-CBG BPJS's database for each B-Class hospital.

Mortality rate ($M_{i,t}^{ID}$) is used as a proxy for health outcomes that measure how better management of a hospital can reduce the mortality rate in a particular hospital. Decreasing of Mortality rate in respected hospital improve

consumer preferences. The mortality rate was defined by applying a binary variable, where 1 indicates a deceased, and 0 is otherwise. The data is available in the INA-CBG BPJS dataset for each patient in the B-class hospital sample.

The first interaction of health quality is between mortality and income group ($MY_{ij,t}^{ID}$: Mortality Rate \times Income Group). This parameter indicates socio-economic and health status behaviour. This parameter demonstrates that reducing of mortality rate in the higher income groups is the capability of the health care service of the operated hospital to maintain its service. If this interaction variable is statistically significant on consumer preferences, we claim that operated hospital has produced enough health care delivery to prospective consumers. While this group is treated well, the lowered income group can be relied on this group. Hence the demand for the highest income group is increasing, and the lowered income group gains the benefit. Otherwise, if the mortality rate is increasing in this group, the result will be different if UHC membership increases the health risk, indicating that increasing health care expenditure will be a burden for UHC sustainability. Income groups were obtained from the INA-CBG BPJS dataset classified according to the class level of service: the highest level is first class (1), and the lowest level is the third class (3), representing the level of UHC premium payment and the patients' level of affordability.

The second interaction is between mortality status and morbidity level ($MSL_{i,t}^{ID}$: Mortality Rate \times Severity Level). These variables demonstrate how health service providers are able to reduce mortality with the highest severity level. When a health service provider cannot deal with the lowest severity cases, then mortality rates will increase, which indicates that the provider lacks both human resources and infrastructure. The severity level indicator was retrieved from the INA-CBG BPJS dataset and had three categories, where 3 is the highest level of severity and 1 is the lowest. This indicator was evaluated and confirmed by the physician to clarify the level of severity.

In order to ensure that our sample and confirm the probability of a model being true. We follow a procedure, according to (Lancsar & Louviere, 2008), that sample meet the requirements for choice modeling (Van Den Broek-Altenburg & Atherly, 2020). The Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) that indicates the likelihood results has the probability of a model being true (the AIC, BIC, and likelihood close to sample data), and confirm that these models are close to population (de Bekker-Grob et al., 2015).

3.2. Data and Sample

Samples of UHC patients and health service providers were supplied by the INA-CBG BPJS online system from 2015 and 2016. The INA-CBG system is based on the Ministry of Health Regulation No. 52/2016 on the Health Standard Service for Health Insurance Services (HIS). The dataset represents 111 variables that consist of 15 variables for patient's id and membership, 23 variables about a primary health service provider, 20 variables for non-capitation, and 53 variables for the advanced health service provider. We focus on advanced health care providers because this data represents the hospital healthcare system. The total sample for both periods is 909.202 samples that consist of 395.016 collected samples in 2015, and about 514.186 were collected in 2016 samples. The total sample for B-class hospitals is 34.6% (314.547 samples) for both periods. For each period, the data was collected about 37.5% (148.236 samples) in 2015 and 32.3% (166.311 samples) in 2016. These datasets are the largest sample than other A-class hospitals, consisting of 17.5% and C-class hospitals about 29.3% for both periods.

Furthermore, B-Class hospitals have a more consistent sample than A and C in terms of the operated hospital (i.e. states, military, private) for both periods and regions. In 2016 the number of a sample that INA CBG BPJS was taken was about 78.49% in Indonesia (292 samples of 372 population hospitals). We expect that this consistent data will improve data variance for preferences and producing efficiency to achieve faster convergence in large-scale data processing. We stated that B-Class hospital data obtained from INA CBG BPJS is quite consistent and has an adequate sample to conduct patient preference analysis in the study.

Although some data is publicly available, patient age, education, waiting time, and address are private. However, the core variables of distance, mortality, morbidity and income group are publicly available. This study focuses on these core variables because they sufficiently represent the patient health choice, as supported by previous studies, e.g. Van Den Broek et al. (2020), Borah (2006), Sivey (2012), Moscelli et al. (2016), Gutacker et al. (2016) and Gaynor et al. (2016). Descriptions and sample sizes for all of these variables are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of hospital variables for Indonesia

Hospital Operation	Variables		Indonesia				
			Number of Patient Samples	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Public	Independent	Distance (km)	216,278	42.35	203.8	0	3,775.50
		Cost (1000 Rp)	216,278	1,098.25	2,366.25	76.9	127,000.00
		Mortality Rate	216,280	0	0.10	0	1
		Severity Level	216,278	0.25	0.60	0	3
		Income Group	216,280	2.85	0.45	1	3
	Dependent	Patient Choice	216,280	1.5	0.01	0	1
Military	Independent	Distance (km)	24,686	57	292.6	0	3,759.50
		Cost (1000 Rp)	24,686	844.5	2,093.60	67.6	56,700.00
		Mortality Rate	24,686	0	0.1	0	1
		Severity Level	24,686	0.1	0.4	0	3
		Income Level	24,686	2.9	0.4	1	3
	Dependent	Patient Choice	24,686	1.3	0.02	0	3
Private	Independent	Distance (km)	73,583	43.1	232.6	0	4,297.40
		Cost (1000 Rp)	73,583	1,115.70	3,014.80	76.7	123,000.00
		Mortality Rate	73,583	0	0.1	0	1
		Severity Level	73,583	0.2	0.5	1	3
		Income Group	73,583	2.8	0.5	1	3
	Dependent	Patient Choice	73,583	1.2	0.01	0	1
	Total Patient Samples		314,547				
	Hospital Samples		206				

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the basic statistics, such as the number of samples and the health service providers that meet the requirements for choice modeling. The BIC, AIC, and the likelihood results (Tables 1) indicate the probability of a model being true (The BIC, AIC, and likelihood numbers are close to the sample observation). This confirms that these models are based on the population.

Table 2 shows the results for all samples of hospital quality parameters in Indonesia. The key variable in the model is distance. This has a negative effect ($\beta_{ijt}^{D,1D} = -0.054$) on patient preference. However, this is not significant. There is an increased probability of patient preference for B-Class hospitals; however, the amount of patient visits is not significant. Patients are unwilling to travel to B-Class hospitals, whether they are state, military, or private hospitals. In the Indonesian context, the results have similar results with the previous study such as Moscelli et al. (2016) and Gutacker et al. (2016) that distance has a negative effect on consumer preference. Otherwise, the statistical test is not significant, which means that distance between patient and health service during period 2015 and 2016 are unable to reduce the distance for health care service. There is not enough supply of health care services to improve consumer preference across Indonesia.

Table 2. Choice model for patient preferences with full dataset from patients in Indonesia in 2015 and 2016

Variables	Mean			Standard Deviation
	States	Military	Private	
Mortality Rate: $\beta_{ijt}^{M,ID}$		-0.557** (0.245)	-0.322* (0.169)	
Mortality Rate x High Level of Severity: $\beta_{i,j,t}^{M \times SL,ID}$		-0.0833 (0.245)	0.563*** (0.208)	
Mortality Rate x High Level of Income Group: $\beta_{i,j,t}^{M \times Y,ID}$		-1.147*** (0.224)	-0.910*** (0.150)	
Ln(Distance): $\beta_{ijt}^{C,ID}$	-0.0544 (0.0355)	-0.0544 (0.0355)	-0.0544 (0.0355)	
Ln(Cost of Health Exp.): $\beta_{ijt}^{C,ID}$	-0.0104 (0.0248)	-0.0104 (0.0248)	-0.0104 (0.0248)	0.00000390 (0.00000308)
Constant		-2.349*** (0.381)	-1.170*** (0.352)	
Observations	648,834	74,058	220,749	943,641
Number of Hospitals	144	18	44	
Bayesian Information Criterion	499,411.6			
Akaike Information Criterion	499,282.4			
Likelihood	-249,630.2			

Robust standard errors in parentheses. Note: *** $p \leq 0.01$, ** $p \leq 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.1$

The cost of health expenditure has a negative slope ($\beta_{ijt}^{C,ID} = -0.010$) and is not statistically significant. The cost does not significantly improve the probability of patient preferences to visit hospitals. The cost of the UHC health expenditure scheme does not affect patient health preferences. This result supports a previous study conducted by Satibi et al. (2019). They demonstrate that the UHC scheme's cost is unable to improve patient health preferences. UHC's cost should be adjustable to meet the quality of health care and improve patient preferences effectively. Suppose the UHC is unable to take this opportunity. In that case, the market will shift toward a private market that can offer greater efficiency and better health service. The UHC should seek to continuously improve the cost of healthcare to ensure efficiency and competitiveness with the private sector.

The probability of mortality is higher in state hospitals than in private and military hospitals. The mortality status for private, compared to state hospitals is negative ($\beta_{i,private,t}^M = -0.322$) and significant at the 10% level. Military hospitals compared to state hospitals ($\beta_{i,military,t}^M = -0.557$) has lower parameters than private hospitals ($P \leq 0.02$). These results support the finding of Agustina et al., (2019) that states hospitals are facing a lack of health care infrastructure and lack of human resources. These constraints are due to limited budget resources to invest in health care infrastructure and human resources. This limited capacity has widened by increasing patient growth and another emergence of new non and communicable diseases (Mboi, 2015). The state's hospitals become over capacity and unable to deliver better health care delivery.

The interaction between mortality rate and high income is high, with state-operated hospitals having a higher value (increased mortality rate) than military and private hospitals. The probability of mortality in the higher income group in military hospitals is negative compared to state hospitals ($\beta_{i,military,t}^{M \times Y,ID} = -1.147$; $P \leq 0.00$). The probability of mortality in the higher income group in private hospitals is also negative compared to state hospitals and is lower than military hospitals ($\beta_{i,private,t}^{M \times Y} = -0.910$; $P \leq 0.00$). Therefore, military hospitals are better than private hospitals, and both have an increased probability of reducing mortality rates in the higher income group than state hospitals.

If we were looking at these results, there is a prospect for the UHC to improve the quality of the health care service provider. This study support previous result such as the Worldbank (2019) report, which demonstrates that the Indonesian middle class is seeking a higher quality of care. Suppose the UHC focus on improving health

care delivery in this income group. In that case, the UHC will benefit from the lower health risk group and benefits from longer terms of health claims besides the lower income group (Gani & Budiharsana, 2018). This potential market should be targeted as the preferential market for the UHC. These results also confirm that the mortality rate and high income in state hospitals are higher than in private and military hospitals—the why state hospitals are unable to perform better of a health service providers. Most of the consumers believe that the states hospital is the only hospital that closes with the UHC. This perception stimulates consumers to prefer to use the state's hospital rather than private and military. These conditions trigger over capacity for state hospitals and benefit health care service for military and private hospitals. These results supported by previous findings suggest that it is necessary to involve other healthcare service providers or other multi-stakeholders to expand health care access for consumers within the UHC framework (Bernales-Baksai, 2020).

The interaction between mortality rate and severity level indicates that patients with a high severity level are more likely to occur in a private hospital than a state hospital. The parameter for this interaction is positive in private hospitals ($\beta_{i,private,t}^{M \times SL, ID} = 0.563$; $P \leq 0.01$). The probability of mortality increasing with severity level is higher in private hospitals compared to states hospitals. Under the UHC scheme, privately operated hospitals have higher mortality than state and military hospitals. However, states hospital an overcapacity to perform adequate healthcare service. States hospital usually has superiority in particular infrastructure or specific treatment. Most states hospitals are usually university hospitals that conduct research and development activities (Mahendradhata et al., 2017). The frontier of medical research have been developed and more advance in states hospital rather than a military or private hospital. Most of this university hospital is equipped with the latest technology financed by the ministry of health or ministry of education to improve global health standards in particular medical treatment.

According to these results we claimed in empirical finding the quality factor effect on patient preferences in Mortality Rate, and variable interaction of Mortality Rate and Higher Level of Income. The state hospital is better to tackle for reducing Mortality Rate in High Level of Severity, whereas Military and Private Hospital have better health care delivery in reducing Mortality Rate, and reducing Mortality Rate in Higher Level of Income.

Furthermore, to plot the result of Figure 1, we predicted the results of Table 1 and plotted in two-dimensional Graph to depict the result in Figure 2. It is confirmed that predicted value of health quality factors prefers to States Hospital rather than Military Hospital.

Figure 2. Plotting Curve of Predicted Consumer Preference for B-Class Hospital operated by States vs Military

Source: Author Estimation, 2021.

We find that The DCE method is a powerful tool for policymakers, such as the Ministry of Health or other public stakeholders. The results from this method produce better insight into how the health policy should be prioritized. According to Table 2 we can elucidate that how government should focus on. For instance, it is necessary to expand and involve the private sector to reduce overcapacity in a state hospital to meet proper public health standards. The government should involve other market player such as private health service providers to expand health care access for the consumer. This policy can improve health care equity with other health care service providers.

5. Conclusions

This study shows that the DCE is a powerful method to assess the priority policy based upon consumer perspective. The result can identify the significant parameter as a lesson for other economies that the policy should be supported by improving healthcare access and healthcare quality. Market access is the first step to introducing health care services for improving hospital access. The government should prioritize more access to the health service provider to attract other market agents, such as the private sector. Improving the quality of health care is paramount to ensure standardization of the health care service. The UHC will be ineffective if those factors are not coordinated.

We recommend Indonesia's UHC caretaker, a.k.a BPJS and Ministry of Health. The UHC should be more efficient for delivering sustainable healthcare. At the early stage of Indonesia's UHC, UHC members improve their demand with lower coverage. Although the flexibility is slight, the growing demand of middle-income groups and state hospital growth stimulates UHC members to use these services. The UHC should improve the dissemination program and offer continuous improvements to healthcare quality. Improving standardization of health care quality through the Ministry of Health Policy for a health service provider is imperative. If these aspects are neglected, the UHC faces financial difficulties. While the members will be unwilling to use the service and pay the membership premium, resulting in the UHC becoming a burden for the state and taxpayers.

We recommend further study; the data set should be expanded into more periods such as 2018 or 2019. The method can be in specific analysis such as assessing consumer preferences in a specific disease and how the UHC's patient response in more specific medical treatment. The method can be refined by applying simple methods such as conditional logit with more sample or simulated method of moment (SMM) to explore with time difference across the sample.

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